

“A more equitable distribution of skills” in Laser Run: What Olympic Performance Data Reveal and the Implications for a More Balanced Shooting–Running Format

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Abstract:

This research is divided into two parts. The first part examines the relationship between running performance (TRT) and shooting performance (CST) in relation to the total time (TT) of the Olympic Laser Run. To this end, an observational and comparative analysis was conducted using data from London 2012, Rio 2016, Tokyo 2020, and Paris 2024, considering gender, Olympic edition, and three performance levels (Q1, Q2, and Q3), both individually and in combination. The results show that, in most contexts defined by gender, Olympic edition, and performance level, running performance has a greater influence on TT. However, shooting performance, although secondary, remains significant and may exert a greater relative influence when running performances are more evenly matched.

The second part examines how the regulatory change introduced by the UIPM—namely, the addition of an initial shooting round (Shot0) to the Paris 2024 format—could influence these relationships. The findings suggest that the impact of this modification depends on the behaviour of Shot0: the relative contribution of shooting will remain unchanged if Shot0 performs as the “average” of all shooting rounds, but it could exceed 26% if its outcome mirrors that of Shot1 in Paris 2024, although it would never surpass the predominant influence of TRT.

As a first practical implication of this study, the sensitivity of the new format incorporating Shot0 is analysed. Its effectiveness depends largely on the performance achieved by pentathletes in this initial round, which is completed without prior running-induced fatigue. In this context, it is proposed that the impact of Shot0 is mediated by psychological factors such as emotional control and the initial pressure of competition, together with the superior ability of top-level pentathletes to manage a first shooting round under these psycho-emotional conditions and in the absence of physical fatigue. For example, in Tokyo 2020, Q1 athletes achieved a 74% success rate in the first round, compared with 57–65% for Q2 and Q3.

A second practical implication considers the potential redesign of the Laser Run format should the inclusion of Shot0 prove insufficient to achieve a more equitable distribution of skills. In this scenario, three explicit adjustment options are proposed: (1) modifying only the running component by reducing the distance per section or the total running distance, which would shift

the TRT/CST balance but presents clear limitations due to the handicap start and the risk of lapping, potentially reducing the clarity of competition positions for spectators; (2) intervening exclusively in the shooting component by increasing its difficulty through structural modifications conceived as theoretical design scenarios—an option that is conceptually effective but more complex to implement because of technological, operational, and spectator-clarity constraints; and (3) adopting a combined strategy involving moderate, fine-tuned adjustments to both running and shooting to achieve a more balanced proportion between the two.

In this sense, our analysis provides a means to visualise, through scenario-based modelling, the potential effects of adjustments to running distance and, more importantly, the limits within which the format can be modified without departing from a coherent sporting framework. The aim is to calibrate the proportions within TT rather than to assume a direct or automatic correspondence between running distance and the relative “importance” of running and shooting. From this perspective, regardless of the design strategy adopted, a key practical recommendation is to evaluate the run-to-sprint ratio in each specific context, **since this “effective balance” is not fixed by the regulations but emerges empirically and may vary according to competitive level, athlete profile, fatigue conditions, tactical dynamics, and the characteristics of the event or season.** Indeed, one of the overarching findings of the study is that the relative contributions of TRT and CST vary substantially depending on the analytical context (sample, competition, gender, running speed, etc.), reinforcing the need for continuous, data-driven monitoring of any format adjustments—not only to assess progress towards a more equitable balance between running and shooting but also to identify unintended consequences, such as diminishing the importance of performance at the target.

Overall, beyond its academic contribution, this study aims to contribute to innovation processes in the design of evidence-based competitive formats. It approaches each regulatory change as a testable hypothesis—one that can be modelled in advance, implemented under controlled conditions, and assessed using clear indicators (e.g., the effective shooting-to-running distribution within TT and its stability across contexts). From this perspective, the goal is to advance design strategies that refine the Laser Run competition format, in line with the UIPM’s policy of continuous improvement and innovation within Modern Pentathlon.

Keywords: Modern Pentathlon, Laser Run, Sports performance, Olympic Games

1. Introduction

The Laser Run has become the decisive segment of the modern pentathlon, as it concentrates—within a few minutes and under intense competitive pressure—performance variations associated with both running speed and shooting accuracy. The intermittent structure of the format, which alternates between running and shooting bouts, means that minor execution differences can translate into substantial differences in total time, particularly in tightly contested fields with high performance density, as is typical of elite competition. In this context, examining how the interaction between running and shooting components is reflected in the final Laser Run classification is not merely a descriptive snapshot, but a necessary step toward understanding why certain competitive profiles consistently gain advantages across different Olympic contexts and format configurations.

Parallel to this growing interest in the determinants of performance, the debate surrounding “*a more equitable distribution of skills*” as a guiding principle for competition design—and its media implications—has recently gained momentum within federative and sports governance contexts (UIMP, 2025a). This framework advocates for a Laser Run format that promotes a more balanced contribution of the skills involved, thereby preventing competitive outcomes from depending disproportionately on a single component. Rather than constituting an empirical claim in itself, this approach represents a design principle that informs format modifications aimed at preserving the multidisciplinary identity of Modern Pentathlon while optimising alignment between the skills assessed and the final competitive outcome.

Revisions to competition formats are common and constitute an integral part of the historical evolution of sport. In some instances, such changes are accompanied by evaluative studies aimed at assessing their impact (Ibáñez et al., 2018; Rennie et al., 2025). Within this framework of continuous improvement, the Union Internationale de Pentathlon Moderne has consistently regarded the Laser Run as a “living” format, open to successive adjustments intended to enhance its sporting value through increased outcome uncertainty, greater media appeal, accessibility for athletes across age groups, and a balanced integration of physical and technical components. In practical terms, the history of this discipline can be understood as a process of regulatory and structural refinement, involving modifications to distances, sequences, and other regulatory elements, both in its role as a discipline within Modern Pentathlon since 2009 (see Table 1; UIPM, 2025b) and as an independent sport since 2015 (UIPM, 2024).

However, a gap remains in the analysis of the respective contributions of running and shooting to overall Laser Run performance, particularly with regard to their internal balance. While the literature and performance analyses have examined the relative importance of shooting and running as separate components, explicit links between evidence derived from Olympic contexts and quantitative assessments capable of informing competition format redesign are often lacking. In a period marked by regulatory changes and proposals targeting LA2028—including the incorporation of an additional shooting bout prior to the first running segment (hereafter referred to as shot0

Table 1. Characteristics of running and shooting at the Olympic Games (2012-2028).

	Running distance			Shooting conditions		
	Segment (m)	Nº of sections	Total (m)	Nº of rounds	Distance (m)	Time limit (sec)
Londres 2012	1000	3	3000	3	10	70
Río 2016	800	4	3200	4		50
Tokyo 2020	800	4	3200	4		
París 2024	600	5	3000	4		
Los Angeles 2028	600	5	3000	¿5?		

— it is particularly relevant to generate evidence that allows anticipation of how the balance between components is redistributed and which performance patterns emerge across different competitive contexts.

Within this framework, the present study pursues three objectives: (a) to describe the relationship between shooting and running components in the overall Laser Run outcome using Olympic performance data; (b) to examine how this relationship varies across competitive contexts, including Olympic edition, gender, and performance groups; and (c) to derive evidence-based implications for competition format design, with the aim of informing adjustments that promote a more balanced contribution of shooting and running.

Figure 1. Pentathletes in a shooting round during the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation* 2024.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study design

This study comprises two clearly differentiated components. The first consists of a retrospective analysis of individual Laser Run performance data from the four Olympic

editions in which the discipline has been included in the Olympic programme—London 2012, Rio 2016, Tokyo 2020, and Paris 2024. The aim of this component is to quantify the relative contributions of running (TRT) and shooting (CST) to the total event time (TT). Additionally, this distribution is compared across Olympic editions, by gender, and by performance level—both independently and in combination—in order to characterise differences between competitive contexts. Given the observational nature of the study design, the findings provide a descriptive rather than causal perspective.

The second phase consists of a simulation of a recent rule change introduced by the Union Internationale de Pentathlon Moderne (UIPM, 2025b), which adds an initial shooting bout (*Shot0*) to the Paris 2024 Laser Run format (5 × 600 m with four interspersed shooting bouts). This simulation quantifies how the distribution between running and shooting changes when a fifth shooting bout is introduced, thereby increasing the shooting component (CST) while keeping the total running distance (TRT) constant. Because *Shot0* would be performed without a preceding running segment—unlike the first shooting bout in the Paris 2024 format, which follows 600 m of running—the projection is implemented using several scenarios designed to estimate plausible outcomes for this initial shooting bout. Specifically, these scenarios draw on each pentathlete’s shooting times from Paris 2024 to establish a reasonable range of variation in the relative weight of shooting compared with running under the *Shot0* configuration, which is then contrasted with the original Olympic format. As in the first phase, this simulation does not aim to infer causality, but rather to quantify the expected redistribution between components under the proposed *Shot0* assumptions.

2.2 Data source and sample

The data used in the first phase were obtained from Laser Run rankings of Olympic pentathletes competing at London 2012, Rio 2016, Tokyo 2020, and Paris 2024, as reported by official sources and international competition results repositories. From these rankings, individual performance records were extracted and compiled into a database including total event time (TT), running time (TRT), shooting time (CST), gender, Olympic edition, and final position. These variables were used to describe and analyse the relative contribution of running and shooting to total competition time. All pentathletes who completed the event with valid TT, TRT, and CST records were included in the analysis. A small number of cases were excluded due to withdrawal or incomplete data (three in London 2012 and one in Tokyo 2020).

In addition, this study incorporates a performance group analysis to compare performance profiles within the same competition. This approach involves dividing athletes into groups of equal size based on final ranking and examining differences between groups (e.g., four quartiles of 25%, as proposed by Reenfret and Clair, 2013). In Laser Run, however, the number of participants in Olympic events is typically limited (36 athletes, except for Paris 2024, which included 18), reducing the stability of comparisons when an excessive number of group divisions is applied. For this reason, we adopted a three-group classification (Q1–Q3), a strategy previously employed by Le Meur et al. (2010) in the first study to examine the relationship between shooting and running performance. From

a practical perspective, these groups represent distinct competitive levels and enable comparisons of the relative contribution of shooting and running to total event time, while maintaining sufficiently large group sizes to allow meaningful interpretation of performance patterns.

The final database consisted of a single Excel file integrating records from the four Olympic editions into a uniform dataset, as detailed in Table 2. To achieve this, coding and formatting criteria were harmonised, and categorical variables (Olympic edition, gender, and performance group) were standardised. At the performance level, all time-related variables were expressed in seconds: TT (total combined event time), TRT (running time), and CST (total accumulated shooting time). The dataset was organised in a standard tabular structure, in which each row represents an individual pentathlete observation and each column corresponds to a descriptive variable, thereby enabling consistent comparisons across Olympic editions, genders, and performance groups.

For the second phase of the study, which examines the impact of the modification proposed by the Union Internationale de Pentathlon Moderne on the running–shooting relationship, a specific subsample was extracted from the database developed in the first phase. Individual performance records from Paris 2024 were selected as the reference edition, as this competition is the most recent, reflects pentathlete performance under the current Laser Run format, and closely resembles the modification proposed by the UIPM. A dedicated dataset was constructed from these records, preserving the same tabular structure and coding criteria, thereby ensuring that subsequent simulations are grounded in empirical data that are fully comparable and consistent with the overall methodological framework of the study.

Table 2. Composition of the sample analysed, broken down by Olympic edition, gender and performance group (Q1, Q2, Q3).

JJO	Gender	Q1	Q2	Q3	Total
London 2012	Hombres	12	12	11	35
London 2012	Mujeres	12	12	10	34
London 2012	Total	24	24	21	69
Río 2016	Hombres	12	12	12	36
Río 2016	Mujeres	12	12	12	36
Río 2016	Total	24	24	24	72
Tokyo 2020	Hombres	12	12	12	36
Tokyo 2020	Mujeres	12	12	11	35
Tokyo 2020	Total	24	24	23	71
Paris 2024	Hombres	6	6	6	18
Paris 2024	Mujeres	6	6	6	18
Paris 2024	Total	12	12	12	36
Total	Total	84	84	80	248

2.3 Variables and operational definitions

The following indicators were used:

- **TT (Total Time)**, in seconds.
- **TRT (Race Time)**, in seconds.
- **CST (Shot Time)**, in seconds.

The relationship $TT = TRT + CST$ is used to ensure internal consistency. In addition, categorical variables were incorporated:

- **Olympic edition** (nominal categorical with four levels, one for each Olympic Games).
- **Gender** (binary categorical: male/female).
- **Performance group** (Q1, Q2 and Q3) was created by ranking all participants by their total time (TT) and dividing them into three groups of equal size, as Le Meur *et al.* (2010, 2012) did in the first study on Laser Run. Thus, Q1 comprises one third of the sample, Q2 another third and Q3 the remaining third, in order to compare results between performance levels within the overall group.

Based on these three variables, the competitive context was operationalised as a composite factor (edition \times gender \times performance group), which was used to disaggregate the analyses rather than averaging across the entire sample. We therefore define *competitive context* as the combination of three elements that, in practice, shape how performance is expressed in Laser Run: Olympic edition, gender, and performance level (Q1–Q3). The underlying rationale is straightforward. Aggregating athletes from all editions and performance levels into a single global analysis may yield an “average” relationship that obscures meaningful patterns. Rather than assuming that the relationship between shooting and running is stable across all situations, we analyse the data across specific combinations of Olympic edition \times gender \times performance level in order to assess whether this relationship remains consistent or varies according to context. This approach allows us to identify whether the relative contribution of shooting and running is comparable among similar competitive profiles (e.g., medal contenders versus lower-ranked athletes), and whether these relationships behave similarly or differently across editions and categories. In doing so, it helps avoid interpreting as universal patterns that may, in fact, be specific to particular competitive scenarios.

2.4 Data preparation and pre-processing

Prior to analysis, the data were reviewed, cleaned, and harmonised to ensure comparability across Olympic editions and the absence of processing errors. First, variable names and formats were standardised, and all time-related variables were converted to seconds. In parallel, the coding of Olympic edition and gender was harmonised to guarantee consistent categorical definitions across the four editions. Subsequently, the internal consistency of each record was verified, and incomplete observations (e.g., withdrawals or missing values in TT, TRT, or CST) were excluded in accordance with the predefined inclusion criteria.

For the second phase of the study, which focuses on the analysis of regulatory change, additional pre-processing was applied to the Paris 2024 subsample, as this was the only Olympic edition used as a reference for the simulation. During this phase, running splits at 600 m intervals and times for each shooting bout were incorporated, allowing the TRT and CST components to be systematically disaggregated and reconstructed with the level of detail required to introduce an additional shooting bout. Because the time corresponding to this hypothetical initial bout (*Shot0*) is not available in the observed data, a simulation strategy based on three scenarios was defined using the shooting patterns recorded in Paris 2024: (a) a conservative scenario, in which the initial bout is assigned a time equivalent to that of the first observed shooting bout; (b) an average scenario, which uses the median shooting bout time as a reference; and (c) an optimal scenario, in which the time assigned corresponds to the fastest recorded shooting bout. These scenarios make it possible to estimate the shooting component (CST) under the *Shot0* configuration and, consequently, the total event time (TT).

2.4 Statistical analysis

To assess the relationship between total event time (TT) and its two main components—running time (TRT) and shooting time (CST)—Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) was calculated between TT and TRT, and between TT and CST. These correlations were computed separately for each analytical grouping: by Olympic edition, by gender, by performance level, and for all their combinations.

To facilitate interpretation, correlation coefficients were transformed into a measure of *relative weight* using r^2 (the squared correlation coefficient), which provides an approximation of the proportion of variance in total time (TT) associated with each component. This procedure yielded two complementary indicators:

- $r^2(\text{TT}, \text{TRT})$: proportion of TT variance associated with TRT, interpreted as the average relative weight of running in explaining TT within the group analysed.
- $r^2(\text{TT}, \text{CST})$: proportion of TT variance associated with CST, interpreted as the average relative weight of shooting in explaining TT within the group analysed.

In order to compare groups effectively, we converted these values into normalised 'relative weights': in each group, the weight of running and shooting are adjusted so that, between them, they add up to 100%.

- Relative weight of running = $r^2(\text{TT}, \text{TRT}) / (r^2(\text{TT}, \text{TRT}) + r^2(\text{TT}, \text{CST}))$
- Relative weight of shooting = $r^2(\text{TT}, \text{CST}) / (r^2(\text{TT}, \text{TRT}) + r^2(\text{TT}, \text{CST}))$

Figure 2. Pentathletes on a running section of the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation* 2024.

2.4.1 First study (2012–2024 Olympic Games): observed comparisons and effect size

In this first phase, beyond reporting correlations and relative weights, between-group comparisons were conducted by gender, performance group, and competitive context. In addition to p -values—defined as the probability of observing an equal or greater difference by chance in the absence of true differences—effect sizes were calculated to quantify the magnitude of observed differences, rather than relying solely on statistical “significance.” This approach facilitates interpretation of the practical relevance of the findings, as p -values are sensitive to sample size and do not, in isolation, convey the size of an effect.

2.4.2 Second study: projection of the running-shooting balance with an additional initial round

In the second part, the same correlational and relative weighting framework was applied, but to variables projected from the Paris 2024 breakdown. With these data, TRT and CST were reconstructed, and variables were generated to simulate the structure of the Laser Run with an additional initial round:

- $CST_{proy} = CST + Shot_0$ (estimated additional initial round)
- $TT_{proy} = TRT + CST_{proy}$ (keeping TRT constant)

In the second phase, effect sizes were not calculated, as the objective was not to contrast empirical differences between groups under an existing format, but rather to estimate the expected impact of a regulatory change under a set of defined assumptions.

Accordingly, results were expressed in terms of changes in the running–shooting balance relative to the format observed in Paris 2024, reporting:

- Δ shooting weight and Δ running weight in percentage points.
- A range of impact defined by the minimum and maximum (and, where applicable, a central value) of these Δ across the three simulation scenarios.

In summary, the first phase provides data-based evidence, including estimates of the magnitude of observed differences, whereas the second phase projects how the running–shooting distribution may change under modifications to the relative importance of each component, evaluated across multiple simulation scenarios.

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2.5 Analysis strategy

Analyses were conducted independently for each phase of the study. The first phase describes and compares, using Olympic Games data from 2012 to 2024, the relative importance of running and shooting in the final Laser Run outcome. The second phase projects, based on the Paris 2024 performance breakdown, the expected impact on this relative contribution when applying the modification proposed by the Union Internationale de Pentathlon Moderne, namely the incorporation of an additional initial shooting bout.

2.5.1 First part. Observational analysis of the Olympic Games (2012–2024)

The analysis of the Olympic Games data was structured into five sections:

2.5.1.1 Relevance of running and shooting in the final result of the Laser Run at the Olympic Games

First, each Olympic edition was analysed separately to estimate the relationship between total event time (TT) and its two components: running time (TRT) and shooting time (CST). These estimates were then used to summarise how the relative contribution of running and shooting to the final Laser Run outcome has evolved across the four Olympic editions.

2.5.1.2 Relevance of running and shooting by gender

The same analytical approach was applied separately to men’s and women’s categories. Considering the four Olympic editions jointly, global indicators were calculated for each category in order to describe differences in the relative contribution of running and shooting to total event time.

2.5.1.3 Intragroup relevance (Q1, Q2, Q3) of running and shooting

The performance group variable (Q1, Q2, and Q3) was used to examine whether the relative contribution of TRT and CST varies according to performance level. This analysis was conducted using pooled data from the four Olympic Games, allowing the comparison to be interpreted within the overall sample framework.

2.5.1.4 Relevance of running and shooting by Olympic edition

The analysis was also conducted by Olympic edition, independently of gender and performance group. This approach made it possible to assess whether the relative contribution of running and shooting remains stable or fluctuates across Olympic Games, thereby capturing variations attributable to the specific competitive context of each edition (e.g., course design or environmental conditions).

2.5.2.5 Relevance of running and shooting by competitive context

Finally, to move beyond overall averages, specific competitive contexts were defined by simultaneously combining Olympic edition, gender, and performance group. Within each context, the relationship between total time (TT) and its components (TRT and CST) was evaluated, yielding a relative weight indicator that summarises, for each competitive context, whether a greater proportion of result variability is associated with running or with shooting. This approach prevents global averages from obscuring meaningful differences across the 39 competitive contexts generated by the combination of Olympic edition, gender, and performance group (see Table 6). In doing so, it allows identification of contexts in which CST or TRT exhibit extreme values, or patterns that deviate substantially from the trends observed when Olympic edition, gender, and performance group are considered separately.

2.5.2 Part Two. Projection of the regulatory change of an additional shooting round

2.5.2.1 Definition of scenarios

Given that the time for an additional initial shooting bout (*Shot0*) does not exist in the observed data, three alternative scenarios were defined to estimate its duration (see Table 3). The rationale underlying these scenarios is to represent a plausible range of performance in this hypothetical bout, using the shooting patterns recorded in Paris 2024 as a reference.

In the conservative scenario, it is assumed that the pentathlete would reproduce in *Shot0* a performance similar to that of the first observed shooting bout. In the average scenario, *Shot0* is approximated using a value representative of typical performance, defined as the median of the observed shooting bout times. Finally, in the optimal scenario, *Shot0* is assigned a time equivalent to the fastest recorded shooting bout.

For each scenario, the projected variables were recalculated by adding the additional shooting bout to the accumulated shooting time and reconstructing the projected total event time. Specifically, the following transformations were applied:

- Projected CST (CSTproj) = CST + Shot0
- Projected total time (TTproj) = TRT + CSTproj (keeping TRT constant)

Using these projected variables, the relative contribution of running and shooting to total event time was re-estimated within each scenario. This distribution was expressed in normalised form (running + shooting = 100%) to facilitate direct comparison across formats.

The effect of the regulatory modification was summarised as the absolute change (in percentage points) in the relative weight of shooting compared with the format observed in Paris 2024 (Δ shooting weight). This indicator was interpreted as the increase or decrease in the relative importance of shooting following the introduction of the additional initial shooting bout.

Table 3. Operational definition of the three scenarios (Shot0).

Scenario	Idea	Operational definition of Shot0	How is applied
Conservative	Repetition of initial performance	Shot0 = time of the 1st shooting round in Paris 2024	At the individual level, using the 1st round of each pentathlete
Medium	Typical performance	Shot0 = median of shooting times in Paris 2024	Representative value based on the set of rounds
Optimum	Best possible performance	Shot0 = fastest shooting round in Paris 2024	At the individual level, using the best round of each pentathlete

2.6 Reproducibility

The study was designed to be fully replicable using the original Excel dataset, following an explicit and stable analytical workflow: (a) data import and format standardisation; (b) application of inclusion and exclusion criteria; (c) construction of analytical variables; and (d) calculation of final indicators. By relying exclusively on transformations of time-based variables (TT, TRT, and CST) and clearly defined filtering rules, the analytical process enables independent researchers to reproduce the results by deriving identical subsets and metrics.

In practical terms, reproducibility in this study rests on two core pillars that apply across the entire project. First, data traceability is ensured, as each observation retains identification by Olympic edition and gender, and its progression through the data-cleaning pipeline can be verified (including detection of missing or invalid values and exclusion of DNS, DNF, or DSQ cases where applicable). Second, computational standardisation is maintained, as all key indicators are consistently derived within the same analytical framework: correlations between total time (TT) and its components, followed by conversion into normalised relative weights.

Building on this shared foundation, reproducibility is achieved through two analytical outputs without the need to duplicate procedures:

In the first phase (Olympic Games 2012–2024), replication involves the exact reconstruction of analytical subsets by Olympic edition, gender, and performance group, followed by recalculation of the descriptive and relational statistics (correlations and

relative weights, and, where applicable, between-group comparisons with corresponding effect sizes). As the dataset originates from the same sources and the grouping rules are fixed, the resulting estimates are directly reproducible.

In the second phase, reproducibility does not rely on the introduction of new data, but rather on the application of an additional analytical module to a specific subset drawn from the same source: Paris 2024 with intra-event performance breakdowns. Using running splits and shooting bout times, the observed components are reconstructed and the projected variables (CST_{proj} , TT_{proj}) are generated by incorporating an additional initial shooting bout estimated under three scenarios (conservative, average, and optimal). Within this block, the primary reproducible outcome is the change (Δ , expressed in percentage points) in the relative contribution of running and shooting compared with the observed format, together with the range of expected impact derived from the three simulation scenarios.

Taken together, the availability of the source dataset and the explicit description of the analytical pipeline—including data transformations, inclusion rules, and simulation scenarios—ensure full replicability of both the observational analysis covering the 2012–2024 Olympic Games and the Paris 2024–based projection. This unified approach preserves a single methodological framework while avoiding unnecessary redundancy between the two phases of the study.

3. Results

This section presents the results in a structured progression from general to more specific analyses. First (Section 3.1), the overall pattern observed across the Olympic Games is described, focusing on the relative contribution of running (TRT) and shooting (CST) to total Laser Run time (TT). Next (Section 3.2), gender-specific analyses are introduced to assess whether this general pattern is maintained or shifts between men and women. Third (Section 3.3), results are further disaggregated by performance level (Q1–Q3) to examine whether the running–shooting balance behaves similarly among higher-performing athletes compared with intermediate and lower-performance profiles. Finally (Section 3.4), these dimensions are integrated through analysis by competitive context—defined as the combination of Olympic edition \times gender \times performance group (Q1–Q3)—allowing comparative identification of scenarios in which the overall pattern remains stable and those in which meaningful deviations or reconfigurations emerge that might otherwise remain obscured.

3.1 Relevance of running and shooting in the final result of the Laser Run at the Olympic Games

In London 2012 and Paris 2024, running time (TRT) accounted for approximately 83% and 80% of the variability in total Laser Run time (TT), respectively, while cumulative shooting time (CST) explained around 17% and 20%. In Rio 2016, the contribution of TRT increased to 86.8%, with a corresponding reduction in the contribution of CST to

13.2%. By contrast, Tokyo 2020 displayed an intermediate pattern, with CST accounting for 16.3% of TT variability and TRT contributing approximately 83.7%. Overall, the Olympic editions exhibit a relatively stable pattern characterised by a clear predominance of running, which explains between 80% and 87% of total performance variability. Within this range, Paris 2024 shows the highest relative contribution of shooting (19.8%) among the editions analysed (see Table 4).

When examining the magnitude of variation across Olympic editions, a change emerges that, although moderate in absolute terms, is relevant from an applied perspective: the relative contribution of shooting increased by approximately 6.6 percentage points, from its lowest value in Rio 2016 (13.2%) to its highest value in Paris 2024 (19.8%). This finding indicates that, while running consistently remains the dominant determinant of total time, the relative prominence of shooting can increase under specific Olympic contexts. In other words, the hierarchy of TT components remains unchanged—running continues to account for the largest share of performance variability—but the proportion of inter-athlete differences attributable to the shooting component is modulated across editions.

Table 4. Percentage of total time (TT) variance associated with running time (TRT) and cumulative shooting time (CST)¹.

JJO	% TT variance associated with TRT	% TT variance associated with CST
Londres 2012	82,9	17,1
Río 2016	80,2	19,8
Tokyo 2020	86,8	13,2
París 2024	83,7	16,3
Media	83,4	16,6

¹The % variance represents how much of the *total time* (TT) behaviour can be explained by the *running time* (TRT) and how much by the cumulative shooting time (CST). In other words, it indicates the average weight that running and shooting have in determining the final result: the higher this percentage, the more important the running section is in the total time.

3.2 Relevance by gender

In the men's category, total Laser Run time is predominantly explained by running time (TRT), which accounts for approximately 85% of its variability. By contrast, women exhibit an even stronger dependence on running performance, with TRT explaining around 90–91% of total time and shooting time (CST) accounting for approximately 9%. Accordingly, shooting contributes slightly more to performance differentiation in men's competition than in women's, where outcomes are more tightly linked to running ability.

Examination of effect sizes indicates that this sex-based disparity in the relative contribution of shooting, while moderate, is meaningful for applied interpretation. Specifically, the contribution of CST increases from approximately 9% in women to around 15% in men, representing a difference of about six percentage points. Although

this does not alter the overarching conclusion that running exerts a dominant influence on total time in both categories, it introduces an important nuance: shooting has a greater relative discriminatory capacity in men's competition. Consequently, small differences in shooting execution may exert a more pronounced impact on final rankings among men than among women, despite running remaining the primary performance determinant in both cases.

3.3 Relevance of running and shooting by performance group

When the full sample of Olympic pentathletes from the four editions is divided into performance groups (Q1, Q2, and Q3), the explanation of total performance remains remarkably stable across groups (see Table 5). Within each group, running time (TRT) clearly dominates the contribution of shooting time (CST). In other words, even when athletes are analysed within comparable performance strata, differences in final results continue to be driven primarily by variability in running performance. In this context, shooting functions as a complementary component with comparatively lower discriminatory capacity.

Table 5. % contribution of running and shooting according to performance group².

Performance group	Contribution of running (%)	Contribution of shooting (%)
Q1	95.0	5.0
Q2	97.3	2.7
Q3	96.7	3.3

²From a quantitative point of view, the hierarchy of the race is confirmed at all three performance levels, although there are certain differences depending on the performance group: in Q1, the relative contribution of shooting is higher, while its lowest weight is observed in Q2, with Q3 in an intermediate position.

In terms of effect size, between-group differences in the relative contribution of shooting are moderate. The maximum observed range of variation is 2.3 percentage points, increasing from 2.7% in Q2 to 5.0% in Q1. Accordingly, while minor nuances are present, they do not alter the overarching pattern: running dominates performance across all three groups, and the relative weight of shooting increases only to a limited extent.

3.4 Overall relevance of running–shooting by competitive context (Olympic Games × gender × Q1–Q3)

Analysis of relative contributions across competitive contexts indicates that Laser Run performance is predominantly structured around the running component. This pattern holds across most combinations of Olympic edition, gender, and performance group (see Table 6).

Tabl 6. % contribution of running and shooting by performance group, gender and Olympic event..

JJO	Género	Q1	Q2	Q3
London 2012	Men	81.6 / 18.4	96.0 / 4.0	93.7 / 6.3
London 2012	Women	86.4 / 13.6	70.6 / 29.4	61.4 / 38.6
London 2012	Total	98.1 / 1.9	98.6 / 1.4	89.5 / 10.5
Río 2016	Men	80.2 / 19.8	79.5 / 20.5	87.7 / 12.3
Río 2016	Women	88.5 / 11.5	96.8 / 3.2	69.6 / 30.4
Río 2016	Total	95.3 / 4.7	95.6 / 4.4	96.7 / 3.3
Tokyo 2020	Men	67.2 / 32.8	45.3 / 54.7	44.8 / 55.2
Tokyo 2020	Women	88.9 / 11.1	80.8 / 19.2	93.9 / 6.1
Tokyo 2020	Total	97.5 / 2.5	98.7 / 1.3	99.9 / 0.1
París 2024	Men	56.5 / 43.5	51.6 / 48.4	93.3 / 6.7
París 2024	Women	12.1 / 87.9	75.6 / 24.4	69.7 / 30.3
París 2024	Total	92.1 / 7.9	92.3 / 7.7	99.7 / 0.3
Total	Total	95.0 / 5.0	97.3 / 2.7	96.7 / 3.3

However, two points that may appear counterintuitive warrant clarification.

First, results reported in the *Total* rows (men + women) do not represent a simple arithmetic average of both sexes, but rather a new estimation derived from a mixed group. Pooling men and women introduces an additional source of variability that may be explained predominantly by one component—most often running time (TRT)—without implying that shooting ceases to be relevant in practical terms. In this context, the TRT/CST percentages reported for the *Total* category reflect which component has greater discriminatory capacity within the combined sample, where part of the observed separation between athletes may arise from structural differences between subpopulations rather than from the same mechanisms operating within men’s or women’s categories considered separately.

Second, under certain specific conditions (e.g., Q3 in Tokyo 2020 and Paris 2024), the relative contribution of running may approach values close to 100%. This does not indicate the absence of a shooting effect, but rather reflects the fact that CST exhibits very limited variability within these groups. When shooting performance is highly homogeneous and contributes little additional variation, differences in total time (TT) are driven almost entirely by TRT, even though CST continues to contribute additively to TT.

For these reasons, primary interpretation should prioritise analyses conducted under homogeneous conditions (i.e., within the same Olympic edition and gender). The *Total* category should therefore be understood as a descriptive summary rather than as evidence of a causal shift in the relative importance of shooting.

Figure 3. Pentathletes in running sections during the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation* 2024.

3.5 Projection of the specific weight of running and shooting to the new format proposed by the UIPM (5 shooting rounds and 5 running segments of 600 metres)

Based on the Paris 2024 data, observed running (TRT) and shooting (CST) times were reconstructed to simulate a counterfactual scenario incorporating an additional initial shooting bout (*Shot0*). Under this scenario, projected shooting time was defined as $CST_{proj} = CST + Shot0$, and projected total time as $TT_{proj} = TRT + CST_{proj}$, assuming that TRT remained unchanged. Following the analytical framework described above, the effect of this modification was summarised as the change in the relative contribution of running and shooting to total time, derived from the strength of their associations with TT and normalised so that both components sum to 100%. Results are reported as absolute changes in percentage points (i.e., direct differences between percentages rather than relative percentage changes). Because the duration of the hypothetical initial shooting bout is not known with certainty, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using three alternative *Shot0* scenarios. This approach allows assessment of whether the main conclusions remain robust or vary depending on the underlying assumption regarding *Shot0* duration.

3.5.1 Reference scenario (Paris 2024)

In the Paris 2024 reference scenario, the model indicates a clear predominance of running over shooting in explaining total Laser Run time at the aggregate level, with an estimated relative contribution of 86.93% for running and 13.07% for shooting. This baseline serves as a common reference point for subsequent projection scenarios, against which changes

in the relative weight of shooting—and the corresponding adjustment in the contribution of running—are calculated relative to the Paris 2024 format.

3.5.2 Conservative scenario (Shot0 = Shot1 for Paris 2024)

Under the assumption that *Shot0* duration is equivalent to that of the first shooting bout in the reference scenario (Paris 2024), the introduction of an additional initial round produces a substantial increase in the competitive relevance of shooting. In this scenario, the relative contribution of shooting rises to 26.17%, representing an increase of 13.10 percentage points compared with the observed Paris 2024 format, while the contribution of running decreases to 73.83%. As a result, this configuration shifts the running–shooting balance toward a more even distribution of component contributions, without reversing the established hierarchy, as running continues to account for the majority of the projected total time (TTproy)

3.5.3 Average scenario (Shot0 ≈ median of rounds 1–4)

In this scenario, the relationship between shooting and running remains very close to that observed in the reference format, albeit with a slight reduction in the relative contribution of shooting to projected total time (–1.16 percentage points). Specifically, shooting accounts for 11.91% of TTproy while the contribution of running increases marginally to 88.09%.

This result is consistent with the logic of the sensitivity analysis, indicating that the estimated impact of introducing an initial “cold” shooting bout depends on how its performance is modelled. Under certain assumptions, the effect of the additional round may be minimal or may even operate in the opposite direction to that observed under more conservative or favourable scenarios.

3.5.4 Optimal scenario (Shot0 = best individual round)

Under this assumption, shooting increases its relative contribution, although to a lesser extent than in the conservative scenario. Specifically, shooting accounts for 17.19% of projected total time, while running contributes 82.81%. In this configuration, the projection indicates a moderate increase of 4.12 percentage points in the relative weight of shooting compared with the reference format, while running remains the dominant component (see Table 7).

Table 7. Relative weight of running and shooting in the total time of the Laser Run in Paris 2024 (reference scenario) and three projection scenarios incorporating an additional initial shooting round.

Scenario	Running weight (%)	Shooting weight (%)	Δ Shooting weight (pp) vs París 2024
París 2024	86,93	13,07	0
Conservador	73,83	26,17	13,1
Medio	88,09	11,91	-1,16
Óptimo	82,81	17,19	4,12

Overall, the results indicate that the introduction of an additional initial shooting bout has the potential to shift the relative balance toward shooting; however, the magnitude of this effect is highly sensitive to how performance in that new bout materialises in practice. Depending on the underlying assumption, the projected impact ranges from a pronounced increase in shooting relevance (conservative scenario), to a minimal or negligible effect (average scenario), and to a moderate increase under the most favourable conditions (optimal scenario).

4. Discussion of the results of the first part of the study

4.1. Patterns observed in the analysis by Olympic edition, gender and performance groups

The results of this section **highlight the clear predominance of running time (TRT) over cumulative shooting time (CST) in Olympic Laser Run performance**, with TRT explaining approximately 75–90% of the variability in total time. This finding is consistent with previous research. For instance, Kim et al. (2016) and Lim et al. (2018) reported that differences between elite and non-elite pentathletes were driven primarily by performance in the running phase of the 4 × 800 m format used at Rio 2016 and Tokyo 2020, whereas variations in shooting accuracy and shooting time were relatively small and, in some cases, even slightly favourable to non-elite athletes. The strong association observed between running speed and overall performance reinforces the role of TRT as the primary predictor of Laser Run outcomes. This pattern was particularly pronounced in Rio 2016 and Paris 2024, where running performance accounted for approximately 85–88% of the total variability in event outcomes.

In contrast, Le Meur et al. (2010, 2012) emphasised shooting accuracy as a decisive performance factor in the original 3 × 1 km Laser Run format used at London 2012, reporting that its influence surpassed that of running speed or transition times, and identifying no marked differences between performance groups comparable to Q1, Q2, and Q3 in the present study. In that context, pentathletes who minimised missed shots were able to complete shooting series more efficiently and secure higher final positions. Shooting thus acted as a tactical “bottleneck”, whereby each missed shot imposed a decisive time penalty, albeit one still smaller than the cumulative cost associated with running performance (Le Meur et al., 2012).

This perspective contrasts with the current findings from London 2012 re-analysed in the present study (3 × 1 km format, TRT ≈ 85%), where CST does not exhibit exclusive dominance and differences in TRT between Q1, Q2, and Q3 (≈ 82–83%) emerge as the primary source of performance differentiation. This shift reflects a rebalancing of the performance structure toward aerobic capacity in the modern Laser Run. Similarly, the relatively low contribution of CST observed in Paris 2024 (≈ 15%) does not imply that shooting is irrelevant, but rather that, within that Olympic context, it was less discriminatory than running.

A plausible explanation is that under conditions of high fatigue and competitive pressure, shooting performance tends to become more homogeneous across athletes, exhibiting reduced variability, whereas the ability to sustain running pace and tolerate accumulated fatigue across laps generates progressively larger differences in total time (TT). Consequently, while shooting remains a critical component of overall performance, running time (TRT) appears to be the factor that most effectively explains why certain pentathletes finish ahead of others in this competitive scenario.

In the pooled analysis of the four Olympic Games, the gender-specific pattern further reinforces the conclusion that the current Olympic Laser Run is predominantly driven by running performance. In men, total time (TT) is strongly associated with running time (TRT), which explains approximately 85% of performance variability, whereas shooting time (CST) accounts for around 15%. In women, this asymmetry is even more pronounced, with TRT explaining approximately 91% of the variance and CST around 9%. In other words, shooting carries relatively greater weight in men's competition than in women's in terms of overall performance differentiation, although running speed remains the dominant determinant in both categories. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Park et al. (2022), who observed that men tend to shoot faster ($d \approx 0.49$), while showing no clear differences in shooting accuracy or consistency compared with women. From an interpretative standpoint, if the shooting component manifests primarily through execution time rather than accuracy, it is plausible that greater competition for shooting speed and/or greater inter-individual variability in that speed contributes to CST being relatively more discriminative in men. Nevertheless, even under this interpretation, running performance remains the primary factor explaining differences in total time.

Interpreting these findings within the Olympic context—characterised by high competitive density and small performance margins—suggests that gender differences do not substantially alter what primarily determines performance, as running remains the dominant component. Rather, they influence how performance trade-offs manifest. In men, faster shooting execution may enable more aggressive race strategies (e.g., earlier departure from the shooting position), allowing CST to retain a slightly greater discriminatory capacity. In women, by contrast, the observed pattern indicates an even stronger coupling between total time (TT) and running time (TRT), with shooting behaving in a more stable and less discriminative manner, and performance variability being more strongly concentrated in the ability to sustain running pace. Overall, the evidence suggests that although shooting continues to function as a potential locus for performance errors—as highlighted in studies using earlier formats (e.g., Le Meur et al., 2010)—in the modern Laser Run the primary determinant of performance is aerobic capacity. This dominance is particularly pronounced in women, while in men the shooting component retains a modestly greater relative weight without displacing the central role of TRT.

Results by performance group (Q1, Q2, and Q3) suggest that the relative contribution of running and shooting to overall performance is not uniform, but varies according to

competitive level within the sample. Consistent with the framework proposed by Le Meur et al. (2010), differences among the highest-performing pentathletes (Q1) appear to be explained to a relatively greater extent by shooting efficiency—reflected in lower time penalties associated with additional shots—whereas running time (TRT) exhibits comparatively lower variability when performance levels are highly homogeneous.

This pattern is consistent with the physiological and pacing framework described by Le Meur et al. (2012), who showed that more demanding pacing strategies increase fatigue and may impair the temporal components of shooting (e.g., increased latency or time between shots). As physiological reserves decline, the time cost associated with shooting is therefore amplified. Consequently, in lower-performing groups (Q2 and Q3), running assumes relatively greater importance due to increased variability in effort distribution and fatigue tolerance, while shooting acts as a multiplier of this deterioration through a running–shooting interaction.

This interpretation is further supported by comparative evidence across performance levels reported by Kim et al. (2016) and Lim et al. (2018). In these studies, profiles closer to an “expert” level were characterised by more robust shooting execution under stress and more efficient management of running pace, whereas more “novice” profiles exhibited greater inter- and intra-individual variability, as well as higher sensitivity of technical shooting performance to accumulated physiological load. Accordingly, the differentiation observed across Q1, Q2, and Q3 supports the interpretation that shooting is particularly discriminative at the higher-performance end, due to its direct impact on avoidable time losses. At lower performance levels, by contrast, running contributes more substantially to the dispersion of final results, as it is more strongly conditioned by pacing strategies and fatigue tolerance. Importantly, this does not diminish the relevance of shooting as a determinant of total time cost, but rather situates its discriminatory role within a performance-level–dependent interaction between physical and technical demands (Le Meur et al., 2010; Le Meur et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2016; Lim et al., 2018).

When examining the relative contribution of running and shooting across Olympic editions, a consistent overall pattern emerges: in all editions analysed, variability in total performance is predominantly explained by the running component. Shooting time (CST), in turn, maintains a secondary yet systematic contribution. At the same time, a comparative trend across editions can be identified, with the relative contribution of shooting generally ranging between approximately 16% and nearly 20%. An exception is observed in Tokyo 2020, where the contribution of CST was notably lower (13.2%), although this does not alter the overarching conclusion that running time (TRT) remains the dominant determinant of total time (TT) in all editions.

As the existing literature does not explicitly examine “Olympic edition effects” on the relative relevance of running and shooting components, interpretation of these trends must draw on evidence from longer time frames and comparable international competition contexts. In this respect, the findings reported by Park et al. (2020), based on a large dataset of World Cup and World Championship shooting rounds (2015–2019), indicate that shooting performance extends beyond accuracy alone and encompasses

dimensions of execution speed and consistency. These dimensions are strongly modulated by competitive pressure and cumulative fatigue across the competition. In particular, a typical deterioration is observed in the final shooting rounds, alongside gender-related differences that are primarily expressed in shooting execution speed.

Figure 4. Pentathletes in a shooting round during the Paris 2024 Laser Run. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation* 2024.

This evidence is consistent with the observation that, in recent Olympic cycles and under conditions of maximal competitive demand, small advantages in shooting time efficiency may acquire meaningful discriminatory power. For instance, the ability to maintain high shooting speed without a substantial loss of control under fatigue may differentiate pentathletes of otherwise comparable performance levels. Such marginal advantages could, in turn, lead to a modest increase in the relative importance of shooting across Olympic editions, even though Laser Run outcomes remain predominantly determined by the capacity to sustain running pace.

Overall, the comparison across editions supports a conservative yet consistent interpretation: running remains the primary determinant of total time, but the competitive evolution of the Laser Run—characterised by increased performance homogeneity and heightened sensitivity to “avoidable” time losses in the shooting zone—may explain why shooting assumes a relatively greater role in certain editions, such as Paris 2024. This interpretation aligns with fatigue–performance mechanisms described for shooting execution under real competition conditions (Park et al., 2022).

4.2. Patterns observed in the analysis by competitive contexts (Olympic Games x gender x performance group)

Throughout this section, the combination of Olympic edition (Olympic Games), gender, and performance group (Q1–Q3) is referred to as the *competitive context*. This analytical approach adds an important nuance to the general interpretation presented in the previous section. From an overall perspective, the results are consistent with previous literature in showing that the running component (TRT) accounts for the majority of the explanatory power of final performance in the Laser Run, particularly when comparing pentathletes within the same competitive framework (Le Meur et al., 2010, 2012; Lim et al., 2022). In this sense, the prevailing pattern indicates that total time is largely determined by the ability to sustain running pace and to manage the intermittent demands imposed by alternating between running and shooting.

However, the *situated* analysis—combining Olympic edition, gender, and performance group—reveals that (a) the dominance of running **is not uniform** and (b) under certain conditions, shooting (CST) can assume a more decisive differentiating role. This contextual variability is relevant because it helps reconcile two perspectives that are sometimes presented as contradictory in the literature: on the one hand, running as the primary predictor of performance (Kim et al., 2016; Lim et al., 2022); on the other, shooting as a potential “bottleneck” when errors occur or when high competitive levels narrow performance margins (Le Meur et al., 2010, 2012).

Specifically, when the race becomes more homogeneous within a high-level subgroup, small differences in shooting efficiency can translate into observable differences in ranking. In this scenario, it is not that shooting “carries more weight” in absolute terms, but rather that it **becomes more decisive** as a factor distinguishing athletes who are otherwise closely matched in running performance. This reasoning is consistent with studies highlighting the importance of shooting speed, consistency, and control under conditions of pressure and fatigue (Park et al., 2022), as well as with research emphasising that the competitive format itself can shift which components most strongly discriminate performance (Kim et al., 2016).

Conversely, when the competitive level is more heterogeneous—for example, in subgroups with lower relative performance—differences in aerobic capacity and fatigue tolerance tend to be amplified, and running clearly regains its role as the primary determinant of total time (TT). This interpretation aligns with the view that the combined-event design may favour stronger running profiles when shooting does not introduce sufficiently large or stable time differentials between competitors (Nunes et al., 2010; UIPM, 2025a). In other words, as variability in running performance increases, the discriminative contribution of shooting tends to be diluted, although shooting remains relevant as a tactical element and as a potential source of time penalties.

Taken together, these findings support an integrated interpretation: while performance in the Laser Run is generally dominated by running, the contribution of shooting to final ranking depends on the specific competitive context. This conclusion is particularly

useful for interpreting regulatory changes aimed at rebalancing the event (e.g., the introduction of an initial shooting round), as their practical effects are unlikely to be uniform across athlete profiles. In some contexts, such changes may reinforce the discriminative power of shooting when running performance is closely matched, whereas in contexts characterised by greater dispersion in running ability, the balance between components may remain uneven unless accompanied by modifications that increase the time cost associated with shooting.

5. Practical implications of the second part of the study

5.1 Sensitivity of the impact of the new format

The results of the second part suggest that incorporating an additional initial shooting round (Shot0) may increase the competitive importance of shooting within the Laser Run; however, **this effect is neither automatic nor stable**. In the projected scenarios, the relative contribution of shooting increases from 13.07% in Paris 2024 to values ranging from virtually no change to substantial increases, depending on the assumptions used to estimate Shot0 time (see Table 7). This sensitivity indicates that the “regulatory effect” does not depend solely on the addition of an extra shooting round, **but also on how this new round performs under real competitive conditions**.

From a design and implementation perspective, the main risk of the new format is that Shot0 behaves as an “average” shooting round for all, or nearly all, pentathletes. If this occurs, the balance between running and shooting may not differ substantially from the event structure observed in Paris 2024 (average scenario: Shot0 = median of all rounds; shooting weight = 11.91%). In such a case, the new configuration would fail to achieve the primary objective of the rule change, namely, to revalue shooting within overall performance. Conversely, if Shot0 yields results comparable to those of Shot1 in Paris 2024, **the relative weight of shooting could increase markedly, shifting the competitive balance towards target performance** (scenario 1: Shot0 = Shot1 in Paris 2024; shooting weight = 23.17%), albeit still under the overall dominance of running time (TRT).

This dependence on the actual performance characteristics of Shot0 has a direct practical implication, but it should not be interpreted solely in terms of regulatory mechanics or implementation uniformity. By occurring at the start of the Laser Run, Shot0 introduces a shooting round under conditions that are largely free from physiological fatigue. In this context, differences between pentathletes are likely to be explained less by accumulated fatigue and more by the ability to perform under pressure during a phase of heightened activation: the immediacy of the start, competitive noise, tactical uncertainty, and the need to “anchor” performance from the very first moment. From this perspective, the effect of the rule change may be mediated by a less visible but potentially decisive factor—emotional and attentional control during the “first shots”.

Figure 5. Pentathletes in a shooting round during the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation 2024*.

The evidence available from the 4×800 m format (Tokyo 2020) supports this interpretation. When comparing first-round shooting accuracy across groups defined by final Laser Run performance, a consistent advantage is observed among the highest-ranked pentathletes. In men, Group Q1 (1st–12th) achieves approximately 74% accuracy, compared with 64.5% in Group Q2 and 57.1% in Group Q3; in women, a similar gradient is evident (71.4% vs. 65.9% vs. 58.1%). This pattern is particularly relevant because the first shooting round occurs before physical endurance becomes a limiting factor. Consequently, these differences point to a mechanism other than physical condition—namely, the ability to regulate activation, control breathing, stabilise attention, and execute the technical routine when competitive pressure is at its peak.

This interpretation is consistent with previous literature on Modern Pentathlon. Le Meur et al. (2010) reported that higher-level pentathletes lost less time in the first shooting series due to superior accuracy, and Kim et al. (2016) confirmed similar trends in the 4×800 m format. Taken together, these findings suggest that Shot0 is not merely “an extra round,” but rather an early test of applied psychological competence, capable of amplifying performance differences from the outset and shaping the subsequent dynamics of the event, including effort distribution and tactical decision-making.

From a sports policy perspective, this implies that the effect of Shot0 depends less on logistical differences between venues—which are largely standardised in high-level competition—and more on how this otherwise uniform context shapes the psychological

and attentional demands of the first shooting round. In other words, even under a homogeneous protocol, Shot0 remains particularly sensitive to situational factors specific to the start of the event, such as heightened activation, pressure to “start well,” and the influence of the competitive environment, as well as to how individual pentathletes manage these conditions. Elements such as the call-and-wait procedure, the temporal proximity between the start signal and positioning at the shooting station, environmental stimuli, and pre-shooting routines should therefore be understood as integral components of the competitive scenario. These factors modulate the emotional load of the “first shots” and can, in turn, amplify performance differences between pentathletes.

Accordingly, it is worth explicitly acknowledging that part of the effect attributed to Shot0 may be mediated by this psychological start scenario. This assumption facilitates a more accurate interpretation of the results: if Shot0 increases the relevance of shooting, it is not only because an additional round is introduced, but also because it creates a fatigue-free shooting situation in which performance more directly reflects the ability to regulate emotions under pressure. Furthermore, if the magnitude of this effect varies across competitions, such variation may emerge even when organisational conditions are formally “identical,” simply because competitive intensity, start order derived from the handicap system, pressure-related factors (e.g., spectators and media presence), and athletes’ responses to these elements are not constant.

Finally, these findings should be interpreted as a descriptive projection based on explicit assumptions rather than as causal evidence. Nevertheless, the observed sensitivity pattern remains informative for decision-making, as it indicates that the impact of Shot0 cannot be reduced to merely “adding a round” to the competition rules. In high-level competition, where organisational frameworks are typically highly standardised, the influence of Shot0 is better understood as the effect of introducing a fatigue-free yet psychologically demanding shooting round at the very start of the Laser Run. Under these conditions, performance is particularly shaped by emotional and attentional control processes inherent to the start phase of the event.

Consequently, the competitive relevance of Shot0 will depend to a large extent on its operational definition—specifically, the temporal sequence, transitions, and conditions immediately preceding the first shot. This dependency arises not because such conditions vary substantially between venues, but because they structure a competitive context capable of amplifying individual differences in athletes’ responses to pressure. In turn, this may influence both sporting outcomes and the comparability of performance patterns observed across competitions.

5.2. When Shot0 is not enough for "a more equitable distribution of skills"

This second practical implication should be interpreted in light of an explicit aspiration embedded in the scoring system itself. According to the UIPM regulations (2024), the scoring framework is designed to ensure that each discipline contributes a similar number of points (approximately 1000) based on a reference performance, such that the final score reflects a *theoretically balanced* distribution across swimming (20%), OCR (20%),

fencing (20%), and the Laser Run (shooting + running, 40%). However, **when empirical competition data are considered**, the effective contribution of each discipline may deviate from this idealised distribution. In such cases, it is therefore advisable to treat this balance as **a reference objective**—what the system is intended to achieve—rather than as **a guaranteed outcome**—what necessarily occurs in practice.

In this sense, **if in practice** the “real weight” of a discipline depends, on the one hand, on how the points tables are constructed and, on the other, on the degree of performance variability among athletes in each event, then any interpretation of balance must incorporate both dimensions. Put differently, **when scoring tables convert relatively small performance differences into large point differentials**, a discipline acquires greater capacity to influence the final ranking; likewise, **when athlete performance is highly dispersed within a given event**, that event will tend to explain a larger share of the overall result. Under this framework, a scoring system may be theoretically balanced while still producing asymmetrical effects in practice.

This dynamic is also evident in previous research. In women’s competition, for example, Im and Donoghue (2022) show that under the 2014–2019 scoring system, the effective contribution shifts towards the Laser Run, which accounts on average for 40.18% of total performance, while fencing falls below the ideal 20% threshold (16.03%). Swimming (21.69%) and equestrian sport (22.10%) remain closer to the theoretical target. The appropriate operational interpretation is therefore not that the scoring system is inherently “flawed,” but rather that **as the sport evolves**—through increased competitive density, technical developments, or performance homogenisation in certain disciplines—**or as rules and points tables are modified**, the discipline that most strongly shapes the final ranking may also change. This can occur even when all disciplines appear comparable in terms of nominal point values.

Following the same logic, **if the scoring system aims to promote an equitable distribution of skills**, it is insufficient to assume that balance by design will automatically translate into balance by effect. Evidence from research on the Modern Pentathlon scoring system shows that the “decisive weight” of each discipline is not fixed a priori, but is ultimately shaped by the specific configuration of the system, including competition rules and point conversion tables. For instance, Lee and Choi (2020) demonstrate that the relative importance of disciplines for final classification can change following rule revisions, while Borisovich et al. (2017) report that the combined event accounts for approximately 41.5–41.6% of the total score, slightly exceeding the share implied by a strictly percentage-balanced distribution. Similarly, Im and Donoghue (2022) conclude that the scoring system can substantially alter the proportion of points contributed by each discipline. Accordingly, **if the practical objective is to approximate a functional balance between skills**, analytical approaches must be grounded in verifiable scenarios and contingent regulatory decisions, rather than treated as a closed or definitive conclusion derived solely from the nominal structure of the system.

Specifically, **if empirical competition data indicate that the Laser Run is determining outcomes in a manner that is excessively dependent on a single component**—for

example, because running absorbs most of the variability in total time (TT), or because shooting introduces disproportionate volatility under specific conditions—then targeted adjustments can be implemented through different regulatory “levers,” depending on the pattern identified. When the imbalance is primarily explained by the structure of the effort, it may be appropriate to consider interventions involving race distances or the distribution of running segments relative to shooting bouts, thereby allowing the less influential component greater opportunity to discriminate performance. Conversely, if shooting fails to penalise performance effectively—or penalises it in a manner misaligned with competitive outcomes—then adjustments that modify the actual time cost associated with shooting performance become relevant, such as changes in how errors are translated into time losses or in the time spent within the shooting zone.

Finally, **if any modification is introduced** with the objective of moving the system closer to a more equitable distribution of skills, subsequent evaluation should extend beyond total time or theoretical point allocations. In practical terms, any implemented adjustment should be empirically assessed to determine whether it alters performance dispersion, whether it modifies sensitivity across performance levels (e.g., from Q1 to Q3), and whether it maintains comparable behavioural patterns across genders. Only under these conditions can “balance” be regarded not merely as a design intention, but as a stable and verifiable competitive outcome.

5.2.1 Intervention strategies to seek a balance between running and shooting

To achieve the implicit objective of approximating an overall distribution of 20%–20%–20%–40%—with the latter corresponding to the combined contribution of shooting and running—it follows logically that, within the Laser Run itself, the relative contribution of shooting and running should tend towards a more balanced ratio, closer to 50/50 than to an extreme 90/10 split. However, **the results from the first part of this study indicate that such imbalance is prevalent, as 24 out of the 39 competitive contexts analysed (61.5%) exhibit a highly asymmetric distribution between the two components** (see Table 5).

From a structural perspective, three main approaches to redesigning the Laser Run can be considered, which in theory would allow progress towards this objective. The first involves intervening directly in the shooting component, either by increasing the number of shooting rounds or by raising the competitive cost or complexity of shooting. The second approach targets the running component, by adjusting the “time space” available for running to determine total time (TT). The third strategy combines both approaches in a moderate manner, shifting the relative contributions of shooting and running without concentrating the adjustment on a single parameter.

The option of increasing the number of shooting rounds is, however, practically constrained once an initial round has already been incorporated. Introducing a sixth shooting bout after the final running segment would disrupt the functional logic of the event, as it would conclude with a static task, thereby undermining the spectacle and the competitive tension associated with close finishes. Conversely, “creating space” for

additional shooting rounds by increasing the number of running segments would substantially alter the dynamics of the event and, paradoxically, could preserve or even reinforce the dominance of running by adding more distance and more opportunities for running time (TRT) to exert influence on the final outcome.

An alternative means of rebalancing the relative contribution of shooting without increasing the number of shooting–running blocks is to enhance shooting complexity. This approach is conceptually aligned with Newell’s Constraints-Led Approach (CLA) (1986), according to which the manipulation of task constraints—such as increasing shooting distance, reducing time limits, or decreasing target size—can destabilise established motor patterns and promote adaptive self-organisation. Under this framework, athletes are compelled to explore more efficient functional solutions, particularly under conditions of fatigue. As a theoretical exploration, we propose that the application of additional constraints to shooting may provide viable means of increasing its relative contribution to total time without altering the overall competitive structure of the Laser Run (see Table 8).

Figure 6. Pentathletes in a shooting round during the Paris 2024 Laser Run. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation 2024*.

More specifically, to increase shooting complexity within the Laser Run, execution constraints can be combined with transitional constraints (Sheaff, 2024). Execution constraints can be organised into two main categories: (a) **accuracy requirements**, including increasing the distance to the target, reducing the effective target area, and/or

imposing control over cumulative hit scores; and (b) **quantitative limits**, such as restrictions on the time available, the number of shots permitted, shooting cadence, or sequential consistency. Transitional constraints can likewise be divided into two broad types: (a) **penalties**, implemented through additional time, extra distance (e.g., penalty loops as used in ski biathlon), reverse scoring mechanisms (reductions in the overall Modern Pentathlon classification), or even elimination; and (b) **bonuses**, including round skips (allowing athletes to omit a shooting round and continue running) or cumulative scoring advantages applied to the overall classification.

Accuracy-based requirements typically lead to additional time loss as a direct consequence of increased task difficulty, particularly when shooting distance is extended or the target area is reduced. By contrast, score-control mechanisms enable the systematic application of transitional bonuses and penalties. Quantitative limits, due to their clearly measurable nature, also permit the consistent application of transitional constraints—such as added time or distance, elimination, or reverse scoring—in cases of non-compliance. The matrix presented below, **although not all of its theoretical combinations are viable due to logical contradictions or practical incompatibilities within the Laser Run**, provides a structured framework for exploring design options aimed at increasing the relative contribution of shooting to total time (TT) without fundamentally altering the competitive structure of the event (see Table 8).

Table 8. Constraint matrix applied to shooting in Laser Run (source: own elaboration).

		Transitional restriction					
		+distance	+time	Penalties Elimination	Reverse scoring	Bonuses Skip round Cumulative scoring	
Execution restriction	Precision requirement	Reduced target	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;"> Competitive format design Greater specific weight of the shot </div>				
		Extended distance					
		Impact scoring					
	Quantitative limits	Time					
		N° of shots					
		Cadence					
Sequence							

These measures do not, in themselves, “guarantee” a specific running–shooting distribution; rather, they have the potential to increase the variability and competitive cost of shooting time (CST), thereby reinforcing the relative weight of shooting within the Laser Run. Nevertheless, they should be interpreted strictly as **theoretical design scenarios** intended to explore how the competitive contribution of shooting might be enhanced, rather than as immediate regulatory prescriptions. Their practical implementation would be constrained by technological, logistical, and economic considerations, including the costs borne by organisers and federations with more limited resources. Moreover, any regulatory modification should prioritise outcome transparency, clarity in the underlying regulatory mechanisms, and ease of interpretation for spectators,

whether attending live or following the event through broadcast media. From this perspective, preserving the legibility and narrative coherence of the competition is a necessary condition for the viability of any proposed adjustment.

The second major avenue for intervention concerns the running component. If the principle of identical distances across all segments is maintained, the scope for modification is primarily concentrated on the total running distance, and therefore on the potential time weighting of running time (TRT) within the combined event. Under this assumption, a particularly direct structural strategy for shifting the running–shooting balance is to reduce the overall distance, as available evidence consistently indicates that running accounts for a substantial share of the discriminatory power of total time (TT). In practical terms, shortening the distance reduces the “space” within which heterogeneity in running pace allows TRT to become the dominant source of performance differences.

However, the feasibility of distance reduction is constrained by the internal logic of the Olympic competition format. In the Laser Run, athletes start with a time handicap accumulated from fencing, swimming, and OCR, which can amount to approximately 1 min 30 s between competitors. This structure implies that, in practice, the athlete who crosses the Laser Run finish line first wins the pentathlon. Consequently, the running distance must be sufficiently long to absorb and render legible this initial time differential. An excessively short distance would increase the likelihood of artificial overtaking and regrouping, potentially obscuring the identification of athletes genuinely contending for victory. Such an outcome would undermine spectator comprehension in a format explicitly designed to deliver a clear and compelling narrative for live audiences and televised broadcasts.

To adopt a realistic approach to potential running–shooting balance targets (e.g., 70%–30% or 80%–20%) at specific race distances, we propose an exercise in *statistical imagination*. This consists of using the empirical relationships observed between running, shooting, and total time across the four Olympic editions analysed in the first phase of this study to estimate, in approximate terms, the reduction in running distance that would be required to approach a given balance scenario. That said, it is important to emphasise a central point: there is no “magic formula.” Table 8 is not intended to promise a fixed or invariant distribution, but rather to provide a reference scale and a calibration tool. As the data from the four Olympic Games examined have already demonstrated, the effective running–shooting distribution is an empirical outcome that emerges from the interaction between event format (distance, number of shooting rounds) and actual performance variability (running pace, shooting times, stability under pressure, and the irreducible limits of the shooting process). Accordingly, any proposed adjustment should be interpreted as a design objective subject to empirical verification, rather than as a deterministic prediction.

Table 9³. Equivalence between target run-shoot balance (TT) and required running distance (5 running sections + 5 shooting rounds).

Running weight (%)	Shooting weight (%)	alpha_run	Total distance (m)	Format (m)	Achieved running weight (%)	Shot weight achieved (%)	Error vs target (pp)
50	50	0,275	660	5 x 132	50,01	49,99	0,01
60	40	0,357	857	5 x 171	59,98	40,02	0,02
70	30	0,4775	1146	5 x 229	70,01	29,99	0,01
80	20	0,6895	1655	5 x 331	80,01	19,99	0,01

³The table translates a target running–shooting balance, expressed as an effective contribution to total Laser Run time (TT) (e.g., 80/20), into an equivalent running distance, while keeping the structure of five shooting rounds and five running sections constant. The calculation is based on the additive model $TT = T_{\text{run}}(D) + T_{\text{shot}}$, where D denotes total running distance and T_{shot} represents total shooting time, set as a reference value. The effective weight of running is defined as $w_{\text{run}} = \frac{T_{\text{run}}}{TT}$, with the corresponding shooting weight defined as $w_{\text{shot}} = 1 - w_{\text{run}}$. Assuming a linear relationship between running time and distance, $T_{\text{run}}(D) = \alpha_{\text{run}} \cdot D$, the value of D that satisfies a given target w_{run}^* (and, consequently, w_{shot}^*) is computed. The fields “weight achieved” and “error vs. target” are then obtained by reinserting the calculated distance into the definitions of w_{run} and w_{shot} , and expressing the deviation from the target in percentage points. The target ratios (50/50, 60/40, 70/30, and 80/20) should be interpreted as effective proportions of total Laser Run time—namely, the share of TT primarily determined by running versus shooting—rather than as a direct function of the total running metres. Consequently, the same race format (e.g., 5×600 m) may yield different effective balances depending on the homogeneity or heterogeneity of shooting times and rhythms within the analysed sample (see main text for further discussion). In this context, α_{run} represents the reference average running pace ($\text{s} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$) used to convert distance into time. The resulting distances reported in the table are not intended to describe the current competition format, but rather to quantify the magnitude of running–distance reduction required to approximate each target balance under the stated assumptions.

Therefore, Table 9 should not be interpreted as a prescriptive “recipe” for achieving a specific distribution, but rather as a tool for situating the required running–distance reduction in practical terms. If the objective is to shift the running–shooting balance towards more demanding targets, **the available evidence indicates that a substantial reduction in distance would be necessary for the change to become perceptible in total time (TT)**. In this sense, running offers some scope for adjustment, but it is not an unlimited lever: achieving more “technical” balance profiles would require large cuts in distance. For example, even a 70%–30% distribution in favour of running would imply a per-section distance of approximately 229 m. At this point, a key practical constraint of the Olympic format becomes evident. An overly aggressive reduction in running distance would limit the capacity of the Laser Run to absorb the time handicaps and performance differences accumulated by pentathletes in the preceding disciplines. This, in turn, would compromise the transparent unfolding of the event, as frequent overtaking and regrouping could obscure the identification of athletes genuinely contending for victory. Such a scenario would undermine spectator comprehension in a format explicitly designed to deliver a clear and intelligible competitive narrative.

Figure 7. Pentathletes on a running section during the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Nuno Gonçalves. In album Paris 2024 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation* 2024.

Furthermore, even when the structural configuration of the Laser Run remains unchanged, the running–shooting distribution does not behave uniformly across competitions. Instead, it depends on whether the race unfolds as a *close* contest—characterised by very similar running paces—or as a *broken* race, marked by large differences in speed between athletes. For this reason, it is useful to distinguish between two typical competitive scenarios, which help explain why shooting sometimes assumes a central role in determining outcomes, whereas in other cases it recedes into the background.

a) **Homogeneous race scenario.** In finals characterised by a high degree of homogeneity—similar running paces and limited dispersion among pentathletes—the running segments tend to generate relatively little separation in time. Even when the total running distance is substantial, the running component contributes less to variability in total time (TT), as athletes complete the segments in very similar durations. Under these conditions, shooting can acquire greater relative weight simply because it introduces more differentiation between competitors, through factors such as accuracy, pre-shooting time management, and hit–miss sequences. From a results perspective, running remains a necessary component of performance, but its discriminative power is reduced because athletes’ running times are closely clustered.

b) **Heterogeneous race scenario.** By contrast, in finals characterised by substantial heterogeneity in running pace—that is, by meaningful differences in actual speed between pentathletes—the running segments generate large time gaps. Under the same 5×600 m format, relatively small per-section differences in pace accumulate across segments, with the result that total time (TT) becomes largely dominated by running performance. In

such conditions, even when shooting performance is technically relevant, its impact on the final outcome may be partially “overshadowed” by the greater magnitude of time differences produced during the race.

Moreover, shooting exhibits a structural asymmetry relative to running, insofar as it incorporates temporal margins and practical constraints that limit its variability¹. Even with technical improvements, shooting time cannot be reduced indefinitely, as it includes irreducible components such as entering and exiting the shooting position, approach time, a minimum functional cadence, and a baseline execution time. As a consequence, in many competitive contexts (e.g., Group Q2 in the women’s category at Tokyo 2020), the dispersion of shooting times tends to increase less—or to become relatively “compressed”—when compared with the dispersion observed in running performance, where differences in pace can readily widen and accumulate with distance. Accordingly, even when the number of shooting rounds is held constant by the rules, running typically retains greater scope to enhance its discriminative power whenever sufficient distance and pace heterogeneity are present.

A third option is to combine both approaches. Modest changes in the architecture of shooting—either in the number of rounds and/or in shooting complexity—together with moderate adjustments to running distance can, under plausible scenarios, produce comparable shifts in the final balance, while reducing the risk associated with extreme modifications to a single parameter. Within the context of this study, and once it has been established that Shot0 alone may be insufficient to achieve rebalancing, this mixed strategy also offers the advantage of enabling gradual, testable, and assessable adjustments.

In summary, the regulatory format (e.g., 5 × 600 m with four shooting rounds) defines the competitive *scenario*, but the effective balance in total time (TT) emerges from the interaction between that scenario and the actual variability of running and shooting performance, as well as their structural limits. For this reason, it cannot be assumed that a 5 × 600 m format will automatically yield an 80%–20% distribution in favour of running: such a percentage reflects an empirical property of observed TT behaviour—namely, which component explains the greatest share of performance differences—rather than a direct function of the programmed running distance. From this perspective, the available

¹ For example, in the men’s competition at Paris 2024, although shooting-round times ranged from 6.7 s to 28.7 s, the *typical* behaviour is clearly compressed. The interquartile range shows that the central 50% of shooting rounds fall between 9.2 s (P25) and 14.45 s (P75), indicating that, in that Olympic final, two “normal” rounds—neither among the fastest nor the slowest—differ by no more than approximately 5 s. This compression is consistent with the structural asymmetry of shooting: even at the highest competitive level, an irreducible base time is imposed by entry and exit from the shooting position, target acquisition, and a minimum functional cadence, thereby limiting the scope for time separation between athletes. By contrast, running readily amplifies performance differences because small variations in pace accumulate over distance. For instance, a seemingly modest difference of 0.5 s per 100 m already translates into a 3.0 s gap over a single 600 m segment, or approximately 15 s across the five running stages. This cumulative difference exceeds the duration of 76% of shooting rounds observed in the men’s competition at Paris 2024, illustrating why running tends to dominate the discriminatory structure of total time under conditions of pace heterogeneity.

data suggest that distributions in the range of 70%–30% or 80%–20% represent more realistic targets for revaluing shooting while preserving the essential characteristics of the Laser Run. By contrast, a perfectly symmetrical 50%–50% balance would imply such a radical transformation of the event that it would likely generate resistance and lack of acceptance among stakeholders. However, the running distances implied by even a 70%–30% or 80%–20% split would be perceived by pentathletes as excessively short and would be operationally unviable due to excessive overtaking and regrouping (see Table 9), despite their potential appeal from a purely spectator-oriented perspective. Under these constraints, the most viable pathway towards a more balanced running–shooting distribution in TT would be to combine moderate distance adjustments with strategies that increase the complexity and competitive cost of shooting.

Figure 8. Pentathletes in a shooting round during the Laser Run in Paris 2024. Author: IOC/Filip Komorous. In album Tokyo 2020 Olympic Games. Flickr *World Pentathlon Federation 2020*.

6. Conclusions

Overall, the results confirm that the running component (TRT) is the primary determinant of overall performance in the Olympic Laser Run, accounting for approximately 75% to 90% of the variability in total time (TT) across most of the editions and competitive groups analysed. Nevertheless, shooting time (CST) continues to make a meaningful contribution, explaining between 10% and 25% of TT variability depending on Olympic edition, gender, and competitive level, with relatively higher weights observed in men and in the Tokyo 2020 edition. Comparisons across performance groups (Q1, Q2, and Q3)

further reinforce this pattern, indicating that the superiority of the highest-ranked group (Q1) is not explained exclusively by running performance. Rather, it is also associated with more efficient shooting execution, which contributes approximately 17–18% of the total performance advantage observed between competitive strata.

Across the four Olympic Games analysed, the relationship between running time (TRT), shooting time (CST), and total time (TT) remains broadly stable. Nevertheless, fluctuations are observed across editions and across specific combinations of Olympic Games \times gender \times performance group (Q), pointing to a form of *situated performance* in which the relative contribution of each component is sensitive to the competitive context. In particular, the identification of subgroups in which CST approaches parity with TRT—such as certain male performance groups in Paris—qualifies a purely global interpretation of running predominance. These findings support an integrated reading of performance determinants: when running performance becomes more homogeneous among high-level pentathletes, relatively small differences in shooting execution can exert a greater influence on final classification. This contextual effect does not contradict the general pattern reported in the literature, but rather refines it by specifying the conditions under which shooting assumes a more decisive role.

In the second part of the study, the analysis of *target balances* makes it possible to formalise the distinction between the nominal event format (i.e., programmed running distance) and the effective performance balance observed in total time (TT). This analysis shows that the relative relevance of running and shooting does not follow automatically from the 5×600 m design itself, but rather from how that structure is translated into time as a function of running pace and shooting behaviour. Within this framework, total running distance emerges as the primary regulatory parameter for shifting the effective balance. To approach more “balanced” objectives—such as 70%–30% or 60%–40% in TT—it would be necessary to substantially reduce the running load per section relative to the current 600 m. Such a reduction would allow the shooting component to regain discriminatory capacity without depending on exceptionally homogeneous race scenarios in terms of running pace.

In practical terms, these results indicate that **adjusting running distance is an effective mechanism for shifting the relative balance between running time (TRT) and shooting time (CST)**, but also that its effect is **neither proportional nor unlimited**. This asymmetry arises because shooting incorporates a relatively rigid baseline component—defined by minimum operational times, technical routines, and transition requirements—that tends to remain stable even when competitive conditions change. By contrast, running time scales more directly with distance, such that reductions in running metres lead to an immediate decrease in the proportion of total time (TT) attributable to TRT. Nevertheless, **the scope for intervention through distance reduction is limited**. Excessive cuts risk undermining physiological demands, disrupting the internal competitive logic of the event, and ultimately altering the identity of the Laser Run itself.

From a competitive practice perspective, the practical transfer derived from the analysis of historical data is to provide an evidence-based framework for the refinement of the

Laser Run. On the one hand, the impact of the new format incorporating Shot0 is highly sensitive to how this additional round actually performs in competition: it may reinforce the relative contribution of shooting if it functions as an effective first round—more stable, faster, or more discriminative—or, alternatively, have only a limited effect on the overall balance if it behaves similarly to an average shooting round. In this regard, the UIPM proposal (2025a) can be interpreted as a reasonable—and, importantly, measurable—policy intervention, whose effectiveness should be evaluated using empirical competition data once fully implemented.

On the other hand, if empirical evidence shows that Shot0 alone is insufficient to achieve a reasonable running–shooting distribution in total time (TT), the appropriate response would not be to abandon the change, but rather to refine it through an explicit design-based approach. Conceptually, three broad strategies can be identified: intervening exclusively in the running component (e.g., by adjusting running distance), intervening exclusively in shooting (for instance, by increasing its competitive cost through higher task demands or more severe consequences for errors), or implementing a combined intervention affecting both components. Available evidence suggests that reducing running distance constitutes a direct and effective means of shifting the TRT–CST distribution, albeit with limited scope, as excessive reductions risk distorting the competitive logic and identity of the event. Conversely, increasing the demands associated with shooting can, in theory, exert a strong rebalancing effect, but such interventions are often constrained by technological, operational, fairness-related, and spectator-understanding considerations that shape the feasible evolution of the Laser Run.

Therefore, a **combined strategy**—consisting of moderate adjustments to running distance together with a controlled increase in shooting difficulty—offers, in many cases, a more nuanced and realistic pathway for rebalancing performance determinants. This approach allows the desired TRT–CST distribution to be approximated without imposing extreme modifications on either component. More broadly, the analytical framework developed in this study makes it possible to *conceptually explore* and quantitatively estimate scenarios of varying magnitude, ranging from incremental to more ambitious adjustments. In doing so, it provides an objective and transparent basis for informed format refinement, consistent with the principles of evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement that currently guide the evolution of the UIPM regulations.

7. Limitations

This study is based on an observational analysis of Olympic competition data. Accordingly, its findings should be interpreted **as associations** between the components of the Laser Run—running time (TRT) and shooting time (CST)—and overall performance measured as total time (TT), rather than as causal effects resulting from experimental or regulatory interventions. Consequently, when considering practical or design-related implications, the appropriate interpretation is that the identified patterns **describe how the system has behaved under the observed competitive conditions.**

They do not, in themselves, constitute evidence of what will necessarily occur following the implementation of a rule change.

A relevant limitation of the present study concerns the **external validity of the findings as they relate to Shot0**. Because the configuration of the Laser Run—and, in particular, the structure associated with Shot0—may be modified through future regulatory changes, **not all observations derived from past Olympic competitions can be transferred directly to the new format**. In other words, alterations in event design may modify the effective relationship between running time (TRT), shooting time (CST), and total time (TT). Accordingly, the results presented here should be interpreted as a robust reference for the formats analysed, **rather than as direct predictions of performance dynamics under the proposed regulations**.

A second limitation arises from the fact that the estimated prominence of TRT and CST depends on the internal statistical structure of each analytical stratum (Olympic Games \times gender \times performance group). In particular, if the dispersion of TRT within a given competitive context exceeds that of CST (or vice versa), or if one component covaries more strongly with TT in that specific stratum, the observed distribution of explanatory weight may be influenced by this internal configuration. Consequently, a greater apparent prominence of one component may reflect higher intra-group heterogeneity in that variable—or greater homogeneity in the other—rather than an intrinsic or absolute superiority of that component as a determinant of performance.

Third, the analysis conducted across specific competitive contexts (Olympic Games \times gender \times performance group [Q1–Q3]) may include strata with relatively small sample sizes. When certain subgroups contain few observations, estimates and percentage contributions become more sensitive to extreme values, and the stability of comparisons across scenarios may be reduced. Accordingly, the interpretation of results in this study prioritises consistent patterns and general trends over definitive conclusions drawn from isolated differences observed in specific competitive contexts.

Finally, in the projection and scenario analyses, the results rely on explicit assumptions regarding the translation of the event format (i.e., running distance) into the effective balance observed in total time (TT), as mediated by running pace and shooting behaviour. These assumptions are useful for formalising practical implications and for comparing alternative “target” scenarios; however, they may not fully capture future changes in the competitive context, such as shifts in overall performance level, tactical adaptations, operating conditions, or additional regulatory adjustments. Accordingly, the projections presented in this study should be interpreted as a guiding analytical framework for design-oriented discussion, rather than as definitive predictions of how the event will behave in practice.

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